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Publications of the Taras Shevchenko Scientific Society as Historical Sources of Research on the Book Heritage of Ukraine

Objective. The purpose of the article is to study the history of the multidisciplinary publishing business of the fundamental Ukrainian organization of the 19th century – the Taras Shevchenko Scientific Society. The object is the scientific book heritage of the Society for 150 years, which is a powerful potential of the educational process and patriotic education of young people. **Methods.** In accordance with the tasks set, analytical and synthetic, systemic and structural, comparative and statistical methods of scientific research are developed and used. This article analyses the collections of rare and valuable editions of the scientific library of the Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (DNU), namely, the collection of publications of the second half of the 19th and early 20th centuries of the Shevchenko Scientific Society. **Results.** The research analyzes the entire collection of scientific works of the Scientific Society of the 19th and early 21st centuries, which is kept in the Oles Honchar Dnipro National University library. The editions of the 19th and early 20th centuries and a book collection of the Canadian branch of the National Academy of Sciences of the second half of the 20th century are valuable in terms of content. Special attention is paid to the study of sources on the history of Ukraine as records of the national book heritage. A selection of modern publications of the Society by subject is highlighted. **Conclusions.** One of the important activities of a scientific library is the disclosure and dissemination of information space regarding its collections. The book Heritage of the Taras Shevchenko Scientific Society is a unique primary source for studying the history of the formation of the national identity of Ukrainians.

Keywords: scientific library; collections; book heritage; the Shevchenko Scientific Society

Introduction

The library collections of Ukraine reflect the national and global historical and cultural potential, which includes the book heritage. In the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war, an important area of library activity is the preservation of rare and out-of-print books, on the one hand. On the other hand, proper disclosure of library collections for the purpose of patriotic education of youth and highlighting of white spots in history became a specific objective. In this direction, the collections of rare and valuable editions that are part of the structure of university libraries play an important role. The collection of the Shevchenko Scientific Society occupies a special place among the significant collections of the Dnipro National University Scientific Library. In times of war, the primary task is to disseminate reliable information, spread knowledge potential, and popularise Ukrainian publications, works by Ukrainian authors, and the works of Ukrainian scientists who shaped the nation and created statehood. The purpose of the study is to highlight the history and development of the Shevchenko Scientific Society's collections of publications held by the scientific library of Oles Honchar Dnipro National University.

Methods

In accordance with the tasks set, analytical and synthetic, systemic and structural, comparative and statistical methods of scientific research are developed and used. This article analyses the collections of rare and valuable editions of the scientific library of the Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (DNU), namely, the collection of publications of the second half of the 19th and early 20th centuries of the Shevchenko Scientific Society.

Results and Discussion

In 1873, the statute of the Shevchenko Scientific Society was approved in Lviv, and its history has been studied since that year. The initiative to found the Society came from cultural figures led by Oleksandr Konysky. One of the society's tasks was to create a publishing house for scientific literature. The society raised 18,000 Austrian crowns, which were spent on the purchase of a printing house and publishing equipment. In 1874, the publishing activities of the Scientific Society began. The first period (late nineteenth century) was called the literary and scientific period. 20 own publications were the first. The most important among them was the *Literary and Scientific Bulletin*. This journal was in the collections of Katerynoslav libraries (the Library of Katerynoslav Enlightenment, the city public library, and the library of the Historical Museum) (Bilaniuk & Stebelskyi, 1977). Of particular note is the fact that the library of the society was founded, and initiated by O. Konysky. The total amount of the fund on the eve of the Second World War reached 300,000 copies.

The total collection of the Shevchenko Scientific Society publications in the collections of the Oles Honchar National Library includes more than 300 copies, which are stored in the Department of Rare Books, the Department of Foreign Literature, and the main book depository.

The basis of this collection is the publications of the 19th and early 20th centuries, which are kept in the Department of Rare Books. Among them are 25 volumes of Proceedings of the Shevchenko Scientific Society published in Lviv. The first edition is the second volume of "Zapiski" (1893), prepared and compiled by Ukrainian activist, historian, and educator Oleksandr Barvinsky (Barvinskyi, 1893).

An interesting fact should be noted - six volumes of this collection of Proceedings have the proprietary mark "Library of the Monastery of St Basil in Zhovkva". The history of the monastery began in the 17th century, and the history of the library began in 1780. It was a large library with both an interesting history and a sad fate (Hrushevskyi, 1903).

In addition to Proceedings, "Ethnographic Collection" edited and prefaced by the prominent Ukrainian politician Mykhailo Hrushevskyi was published by the society in 1895 in Lviv. The basis of the publication is "Galician Folklore" by Osip Rozdolsky, and "Ukrainian Human Fictions", collected by Opanas Timchenko.

In 1899 the Ethnographic Commission of the Shevchenko Scientific Society prepared "Materials for Ukrainian-Russian Ethnology" edited by Ukrainian ethnographer, anthropologist, archaeologist, and museum historian Khvedir Vovk. The publication is notable for its appendices compiled by Khv. Vovk. The index, a lot of illustrative material, and drawings are useful. Tables with illustrations of Easter egg ornaments make a pleasant impression (Vovk, 1899).

The Historical and Philosophical Section of the Shevchenko Scientific Society worked on individual texts – historical studies of the geographical territories of Ukraine (for example, the "Collections" – volume 5 "Materials on the Cultural History of Galician Rus' of the 18th – 19th centuries" edited and prefaced by Ivan Franko (1902). Valuable for researchers are the indices of literature and archival materials, geographical, name, and subject; volume 9 contains Mykhailo Hrushevsky's famous work "History of Ukraine-Rus" (1906).

The activities of the Archaeographic Commission of the Shevchenko Scientific Society are associated with the name of M. Hrushevsky. Thus, he worked on collecting materials on the socio-political and economic history of Western Ukraine, and in 1906, these "Materials" were published in a separate volume containing historical documents and acts.

The Department of Rare Books has copies from the series "Sources on the History of Ukraine-Rus". The fifth volume is devoted to the history of Galicia, edited and collected by Serhii Tomashevskyi, a physician and public figure (1901). The seventh volume contains "Descriptions

of the Kingdoms in the Russian Lands" (1903), edited by M. Hrushevsky and dedicated to the properties of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth (16th century). The publication was prepared in Polish and Ukrainian. Volume 22 "Diary of Yakiv Markovych" (1913), edited by historian and genealogist Vadym Modzalevskyi, is valuable as a memoir source. The diary covers the history of the Hetmanate (18th century). The author is a Ukrainian writer, a student of Feofan Prokopovych. This volume is a continuation of O. Lazarevsky's publication "Diary Notes of Yakov Markovych" (1859), which is also available in the scientific library.

In the early 20th century, the activities of the Philological Section began. In 1906, the seventh volume was published under the title "Mykhailo Drahomanov's Research on Ukrainian Folk Literature and Writing". Another name of interest to historians and philologists is Mykhailo Pavlyk, a Ukrainian writer, publicist, and public figure, who edited the volume and prepared the foreword.

The society's activities covered not only the social sciences and humanities. Members of the society also drew attention to the development of natural and medical sciences. Thus, in the early 20th century, the Collections of the Mathematical, Natural History, and Medical Section, which worked at the society, became valuable in terms of content. For researchers, the publications are interesting because of their editorial staff, namely, Ukrainian scientists: the educator and the linguist I. Verkhratskyi, the mathematician V. Levytskyi, the geographer and the ethnographer S. Rudnytskyi. Professional articles on topical issues were selected for publications, including those by Ukrainian scientist in the field of chemistry and physics Y. Hirniak; the physician and the educator S. Murachevska-Okunevska; the physician Osyp Dakura, one of the first authors of scientific works in Ukrainian. The first collection on medical issues of the late 19th century was the "Medical Collection". The Scientific Library has volume 3 (1898) and volume 8 (1901 and 1902). They are written in two languages: Ukrainian and German and there is an index. A medical collection, as stated in the introduction: "This series is the first generalized work of the Shevchenko Scientific Society on this subject", is a professional publication (Verkhratskyi, Levytskyi, & Rudnytskyi, 1907; Ozarkevych, 1898).

The book collection of the Shevchenko Scientific Society of Canada is kept in the Department of Foreign Literature and is also extensive. The "Collections of Scientific Papers" of 1972, 1977, 1993, and 1999 are jubilee editions full of interesting facts and events from the history of the society. The presence of the logo on the book covers is valuable. The Paris edition of the 1955-1957 Encyclopaedia of Ukrainian Studies (10 volumes) edited by Volodymyr Kubiyovych, professor, Ukrainian geographer, and active public figure, deserves special attention. Articles about the Dnipro region, including higher education institutions and industrial enterprises are of special interest (Kubiiovyc, 1957).

Some works by the leaders and representatives of the diaspora of the Shevchenko Scientific Society are of particular interest: Vasyl Veriga (1986) and Bohdan Stebelsky (1991). Their articles are devoted to the history and old culture of Ukraine.

In the 20th century, the society's members were engaged in publishing serial publications. Thus, the Ukrainian Archive series published local history publications with encyclopedic content: "Buchach and Buchachchyna" (1972), prepared for the 100th anniversary of the Scientific Society, 924 pages, with maps, an index of names, an index of photographs (234 items); "Boikivshchyna: a collection of materials on geography, history, ethnography, and everyday life (1980). These publications are of a high scientific level, fundamental in content, and unique in the number of countries (three to five) that participated in the publishing. The preface is relevant, stating that the purpose of the publication is to fill "the gaps in the reflection of the true reality in the history of the regions, culture, and creativity of the Ukrainian people..." (Utrysko, 1980). This series is an example of printing art.

An important area of the Society's activity is popularisation, promotion, and encouragement to read Ukrainian fiction. Established in Kolomyia in 1903, Ukrainiska Naypryadnya Publishing House was known in the 20s and 30s for preparing and publishing Bohdan Lepkyi's works *In a Quiet Evening*, *Motrya*, and *Baturyn in Leipzig*. The beautifully decorated editions of the same format and with the publisher's logo contain Ukrainian ornaments and drawings.

The publishing activities of the Shevchenko Scientific Society continue to this day. In the 21st century, the collections of the Scientific Library of DNU traditionally include modern collections of the Society's works: "Proceedings" (25 vols.), new series "Theatre Studies", "Chemistry and Biochemistry", "Geophysics" in "Proceedings of the Shevchenko Scientific Society", new volumes of the "Medical Collection".

Created in the 19th century and preserved until the 21st century, the book collections and some rare copies are thorough sources for research on the history and culture of Ukraine, publishing, and librarianship. The library's collections contain valuable and useful materials for comprehensive research on the history of Ukrainian book printing, and the history and development of culture, education, and science. The library researches the collections and engages students and postgraduates to work with publications of the 19th – early 20th centuries. The study of the collections as a whole or individual copy will allow us to imagine more realistically the historical processes that took place in the Ukrainian lands of this period, to create a true picture of the historical identity of the Ukrainian people. The Scientific Library participates in the meetings of the historical student group, where we offer thematic literature reviews. One of the most relevant forms of popularisation is conducting classes, lectures, and excursions for students based on the materials of the rare books collection. The department's collections are used by students of various faculties in their educational and research work. The fruitful cooperation between the library and the faculties results in the creation of interesting, creative, and useful projects.

Conclusions

The publications of the Shevchenko Scientific Society have scientific and cultural value and are recognized by the Ukrainian and world community. The book *Heritage of the Shevchenko Scientific Society* is a valuable source for studying the history of the Ukrainian nation, its customs, traditions, culture, science, and language. The Scientific Library of the Oles Honchar Dnipro National University is proud of the solid scientific achievements of the world-famous Ukrainian organization and uses various forms of popularisation. In today's environment, it is important to disseminate information about the society's fruitful activities and highlight its contribution to the history of national cultural heritage.

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Видання Наукового товариства імені Тараса Шевченка як історичні джерела досліджень книжкової спадщини України

Мета статті полягає у дослідженні історії різногалузевої видавничої справи ґрунтовної української організації XIX ст. - Наукового товариства імені Тараса Шевченка (НТШ). Об'єктом є наукова книжкова спадщина товариства за 150 років, що є потужним потенціалом освітнього процесу та патріотичного виховання молоді. **Методика.** Відповідно до поставлених завдань розроблені та використовуються аналітико-синтетичний, системно-структурний, порівняльний та статистичний методи наукових досліджень. В даній роботі проаналізовано фонди рідкісних і цінних видань наукової бібліотеки Дніпровського національного університету імені Олеся Гончара (ДНУ), а саме – колекція видань другої половини XIX – початку XX ст. Наукового товариства імені Шевченка. **Результати.** Під час дослідження проаналізовано цілісну колекцію наукового доробку НТШ XIX – початку XXI ст., яка зберігається в університетській книгозбірні ДНУ імені Олеся Гончара. Цінними за змістом є видання XIX – початку XX ст. і колекція книг канадської філії НТШ другої половини XX ст. Особливу увагу приділено вивченню джерел з історії України як пам'яток національної книжкової спадщини. Висвітлено підбірку сучасних видань товариства за тематикою. **Висновки.** Одним з важливих напрямків діяльності наукової бібліотеки є розкриття та поширення інформаційного простору щодо фондових колекцій. Книжкова спадщина НТШ імені Тараса Шевченка є унікальним першоджерелом з вивчення історії формування національної самосвідомості українців.

Ключові слова: наукова бібліотека; фондові колекції; книжкова спадщина; Наукове товариство імені Шевченка

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